

EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION WITH STUDENTS

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This article deals with the role of effective communication of the teachers with their students. The author of the article carries out an experiment. She makes a survey among the different teachers. The teachers work with the students of different age groups. For her survey the author presented five questions to the teachers. The experienced teachers answered the questions. They talked about their own experience. The explanation of different challenging situations made the teachers think over the solution of the problem. Every child must be treated like an adult and like a personality if we want to see him a perfect person in future. Sharing their opinions and views on this problem the teachers did their best to explain the best ways of creating effective communication with the students.

Keywords: Teacher, students, children, communication, interactive games.

Introduction:

Communication is the best and the only way that people can know each-other, understand each-other's feelings, thoughts and needs. As the great Greek philosopher Socrates says: "Speak, so that I may see you" [1]. Thus while communicating one can understand, know and feel his or her interlocutor's inner world, his thoughts and morality.

As we know our students are our future and we hope that the future of the mankind will depend on them we should determine the role of effective communication with the students as well. When we talk about effective communication with students, the role of a teacher is very important here.

During the teaching process, I prepared a questionnaire in order to increase students' interest in reading and learning. We live in the century of the Internet, sensor mobile phones which draw the attention of young generation mostly. Among the means and ways of the attractive entertainment communication loses its value day by day. As a result the younger generation become alienate and sometimes they are outsiders of the events happening around them and they are not able to react what is happening around them. In this situations the role of a real teacher is very necessary. The teachers' intrusion sometimes becomes boring. As Penny Urr states: "During the latter part of the twenties century, there was a strong reaction against the old-fashioned image of the teacher as dictator and lecturer. As a result teachers have been encouraged to see themselves mainly as supporters of learning rather than enforcers of it, and as "facilitators" who help students how to think rather than "tellers" who teach facts" [2,16]. So the teacher shouldn't dictate the students what to do, he can simply explain the current situation and reveal the student's possibilities for them. Advising and directing the students may save them from making serious mistakes. In order to reveal the secrets of experienced teachers' behaviour in complicated situations and their knowledge about solving the children's difficulties and how they can create effective communication with their students it is important to know how to approach and treat them. At the same time as a teacher I'd much like to be benefited from the experiences of other teachers and to know how

they find ways to solve the students' problems in difficult situations. The teachers from a few countries of the world and teachers who work with the children of different age groups participated in this survey, talking about their personal experiences.

The idea I really like is the world famous scientist Dr. Richard Feynman's concept which says: "Students don't need a perfect teacher. Students need a happy teacher, who's gonna make them excited to come to school and grow a love for learning" [3]. Teachers may know the subject they teach perfectly but it can be hard for them to arouse interest of the learners in the subject or to enjoy from the lesson. So if the students enjoy the lesson, they will never give up learning it and they will never miss the lesson purposely.

Based on this idea, it can be said that the teacher should be energetic, understanding and positive during the teaching process. I started the survey with the following questions.

1. How to make students love the habit of reading books, which plays a very important role in the learning process and for our personal development?

Here I'd like to share the opinions of some teachers from my motherland and abroad with you.

"Encourage to read anything they enjoy, in any format - hard copy and digital. If they don't enjoy books, then maybe they enjoy magazines. When I have had reluctant readers, I have tried to find out what they enjoy and found books that may interest them. There's a book out there for every reluctant reader. They need to see that it's fun and enjoyable and not a chore. In schools that I have worked in we have had authors visit the school. We take part in World Book Day, where the children come to school dressed as their favourite character. They love it [Helen Stokes]."

"We could try to find some content that can draw their attention. Thus, we need first to ask what kind of books they might enjoy reading and recommend such books. Each student has his own taste in life and books can support this tendency. (Arzu Tagiyeva)"

"Talk with students a lot, give examples from literal works and real life" [Afet Musayeva].

"I would explain how reading will affect their future development. I would like to present myself as a

living example. I would emphasize the changes that reading has made in my life. And then I would get my students love the subject. I would express the importance of the subject I teach. (Nigar Aliyeva)

Assign reading challenges to students. Give them a good convincing reason, why they need to read? Choose interesting, funny, short stories to read, and track their reading activity indirectly by giving them small tasks to accomplish each step at time. As a teacher, you can read for your students, in a compelling, captivating way, that may capture their interest, thus push them to try reading by themselves” [Manel Abidi].

The teachers talked about different interesting ways of teaching children. In my opinion the best way we can do it together by sharing our experiences. Every child pays attention to what his or her parents usually do. If we tell them to read books or reading is important it is not enough because they always see what we do. Especially if they find the difference between what we say and what we do they try to repeat what we do. The children are the mirror of their parents. Here I want to share a Turkish teacher- Erkan Eroglu’s best opinion on this question. He says: *“We should set an example for children by demonstrating our own reading habits. We should spend time on books at home and make this activity enjoyable. In short, we should be role models. Book selection is very important. Helping students choose books that interest them will encourage students to read. It is important to choose books that are appropriate for their age and interests. Creating a cozy reading space at home or in the classroom will increase their love for books. By donating books, you can increase children’s desire to read. Regular reading habits should be established by allocating a certain period of time as reading hours every day. We should create reading groups or book clubs and give students the opportunity to discuss and share books. Children should read novels, comic books, story books, science fiction, We need to introduce them to different types of books such as adventure. This way we can discover their interest and increase their love for books. Remembering that every student’s reading speed and interest level is different, we should be patient and try to develop reading habits without forcing them” [Erkan Eroglu].*

I want to mention that I agree with Erkan Eroglu. We can do it both at school and as well as at home. We can share our opinions with them and they also do it with us. As a result they can choose books, they can create their own library and at the end reading will be interesting activity for them

2. Tell us about a challenging situation in your classroom with your students that you have managed successfully?

Some teachers answered this question talking about their own experiments. First of all I’d like to mention that teacher is a person that must understand every child or every student in different situation. Of course the teacher has to find different ways in various and hard situations. I think that every teacher mustn’t raise his or her own voice during the lesson. The teacher mustn’t threaten students with giving

them bad marks. I inquired some teachers about this question. In my opinion if a teacher sees a challenging situation in the classroom, one of the best ways to solve it is to give them a group or pair work. In my own experiment I also see that group and pair works give best results. Students also like group and pair working. If we see any problem between them we must give them a task to do together. In this case they can understand each-other and they try to do exercises together. Of course we must motivate them. I want to mention that for this question Erkan Eroglu told about his best experiment. He has 17 years experience of teaching at different schools in different cities. He shared his experience with us:

“Some time ago, in my classroom, there was a problem of conflict and lack of understanding among the students. To solve this problem I organized activities and discussions to make students aware of emotional intelligence. This helped them develop empathy and understand others’ points of view. I organized interactive games and role-playing activities in the classroom to encourage good communication skills. Open communication between students helped them solve problems more effectively. I taught students problem solving strategies. These included problem solving, mediation, and mutual understanding. I encouraged students to work on group projects. This allowed them to collaborate and appreciate different perspectives. I helped students understand their responsibilities and boundaries by having discussions about acceptable behaviors and norms in the classroom. As a result, absenteeism among students was reduced and a more positive classroom environment was created. By developing emotional intelligence and communication skills, students began to deal with problems in a healthier way. This experience provided students with important skills in problem solving and collaboration” [Erkan Eroglu].

Other teachers’ opinions on this matter are also interesting as every teacher introduces her own share to complete the solution of this problem and I find their ways of teaching more creative, productive and beneficial.

“Chemistry is understood as a difficult and uninteresting subject. They started to like it after explaining the innovations related to chemistry in the workplaces that they want to work nowadays” [Aysel Gasimzade].

“I teach languages in schools in the UK. Often the students don’t want to learn a language because it’s difficult and they don’t see the point in learning it. I have had students who try to disrupt the classroom as a result and try to prevent other students learning. I will talk to the students and I try to introduce activities to make languages more fun. Sometimes this works. I try to use positive reinforcement to achieve good behaviour but if this does not work, then I keep them in at break. If necessary I will report them to the headteacher and I will speak to their parents. I rarely get to this point” [Helen Stokes].

“Once, one of my B1 students admitted that she was not able to focus on any reading material that I had set as homework. We talked through this problem

with her and finally found a piece of reading that caught her attention. She enjoyed the whole book without any complaints which solved her reading issues for a long term" [Arzu Tagiyeva].

3-How to build confidence and self-esteem in students?

We should emphasize the areas where students are successful by giving them regular positive feedback. This can boost their self-esteem.

"Celebrating any achievement and appreciating students for these achievements boosts self-esteem. We must give students age-appropriate responsibilities. Allowing them to make their own decisions and solve their own problems will help develop their sense of independence. Students need to be helped to discover their interests and talents. Getting them to recognize their strengths can boost their self-esteem. I need students to set goals that contain reasonable expectations. When they achieve achievable goals, their self-esteem will increase. We need to inculcate in students the habit of positive self-talk. They need to learn how to speak encouragingly, not criticizing themselves. By encouraging empathy, if we teach students to respect others and respect themselves, we take a step toward understanding the feelings of others, which in turn increases self-confidence and self-esteem" [Erkan Eroglu].

"Lots of positive reinforcement, praise even for small steps. It's important to let them feel appreciated for the efforts they put in. In language learning, I go at their pace and I never put the students into a difficult situation"[Helen Stokes].

"Motivation is key. Give them leadership when it comes to teamwork. Listening to them, and giving value to them and to what they say, under the frame of respect. Mutual respect, as a teacher you need to respect your student, no matter how old is he. Avoiding frustrating comments. Celebrating their little steps, and tell them how good they are when they try their best" [Manel Abidi].

So we can mention that it is important for every child to be listened in order to be confident and possess self-esteem. We must be good listeners. They have their own ideas, thoughts, of course, Children want to share them with their parents and their teachers. If we don't listen to them, it'll create problems in the future.

4- Is it right for the family to interfere with a student's career choice? Why?

Jeremy Harmer says: "If students are always doing what, and only what, they are told to do, there is very little chance for them to become truly autonomous" [4,104]. Each student is a person and he has his own life and he should live his life independently in order to possess his own opinion and point of view. The student must be able to be an active participant in decision-making process and to find an appropriate solution in every complicated situation. He himself decide what profession will be suitable for him.

The students should always make their own choices when it comes to a career. Advice is fine but interference- definitely not. It's the student's choice and their life. (Helen Stokes).

Although it is not appropriate to penetrate a student's whole life choice without even asking for their

own opinion, I think it is crucial for parents to play a role in this direction. Students are independent individuals who can and must develop their autonomy in career choices. However, as all young people could, they also might have some difficulties and be misdirected by their emotions. As experienced adults, parents should take the responsibility to prepare the next generation for the real life, which they are not wholly aware of. However, a delicate balance should always be preserved and students shouldn't be forced to do which they actually do not want to. (Arzu Tagiyeva)

Sometimes the family can only give advice. But the decision must be only student's, because it is his/her life (Afet Musayeva)

"It is important for families to play a role in students' career choices, but this role should be one of supports and guidance. Allowing a student to choose a career based on their own interests and abilities often leads to a more fulfilling career choice. If they approach knowing what their child can and can't do, they should approach it with options rather than intervention". (Erkan Eroglu)

Concerning this question all teachers stated parents shouldn't interfere their children's lives. But they can give them their advice. I also think so. If we reject their choice immediately, it will make children lose self-esteem. That is why we must listen to them and give them useful advice.

5 How would you deal with a violence victim student?

Only by talking (Afet Musayeva)

Try to understand the student's feelings and experiences. His emotional needs and experiences should be respected. We should try to bond with him by building empathy. You need to make the student feel safe. They need to know that the violence is over and you are there to support them. We need to create an environment where they can be sure they are safe, with the help of an adult if necessary. We must communicate openly and honestly with the student and give him the opportunity to express himself. We need to make them feel free to speak up. It is important to provide professional help to a student who has been bullied. Don't forget to contact the school guidance service or a psychologist. Professional help will play a big role in the emotional recovery process. Every bullied student is different, so it's important to approach each situation individually. Providing professional help and emotional support is important to support the student's recovery process. (Erkan Eroglu)

It is necessary to make him feel that he is not to blame for the violence. An environment should be created where he can express his feelings, and if necessary, seek professional help. (Emine Korkmaz)

The most important fact in effective communication is talking. Yes, it may seem an easy way but it is the most important way because they need it more. Every child or student wants to be listened or to be heard by their teachers. Dr Dogan Cuceloglu says: "The teacher must listen to his student... Those who wasn't listened to in his childhood could hardly learn to listen to himself. If the father and mother don't listen to their child and if the teacher doesn't listen to the child

in class, the mind and feelings of that child can't improve" [6,109].

Communication takes the most important part in our daily life. Effective communication with students is the most important item in teaching. I want to mention my favourite professor- Dr Dogan Cuceloglu's words "We expect to become a man from the child whom we do not treat like a man" [5]. Thus in order to be surrounded with honest, kind, firmly, affectionate, clever, diligent, hard-working, sincere and perfect men in future the children must be treated like our own friends, our colleagues and grown-ups. I think it is necessary to let them know their decisions, thoughts, opinions are valuable and urgent for us and we can learn from them as well.

Conclusion

At the end I want to speak about my own experience. I teach English at the university. One of my students passed her school exam in the Russian language but she wanted to learn English and was afraid of beginning learning it in a short time. I told all my students they shouldn't worry when they begin learning languages. Of course my other students know English because they passed exam in this language except that student. I motivated that student every lesson. I said: "It is possible you can do it, I believe you". During our lessons I observed that my words gave her self-confidence. Sometimes she found correct answers while we were doing exercises even when others made mistakes. She passed an exam successfully. As a young teacher it makes me so happy. I always said: "You can

do it and it is possible. I believe you my dear". My words encouraged her and gave her trust in herself. I see it in her eyes. She studies in the faculty of Chemistry and wants improve her English.

As teachers said above the most important problem is we must understand our students in different situations. They come from different families and they have different characters. That is why I think that in different situations we should help them form their outlook, create their own world and not to lose their trust and hope to overcome difficulties without losing temper, hurting others, making serious mistakes.

I think it would be useful if we want to make our lessons more interesting and our students to get great results, we must pay attention to these 5 questions. The teachers from the different countries have already expressed their opinions on this challenging problem and answered these questions.

The teachers of English Language, English Literature, Mathematics, Chemistry, Turkish language and private school teacher- they all mentioned one important problem: we must take into consideration all these features from our students' point of views, understand them and help them. The word "teacher" has an extensive and multilateral meaning . A teacher must be a person who doesn't only teach you any subject, but also he or she must be the person who can touch your life, give you a hand when you need it, you can trust him or her in every situation.

At the end I'd much like to thank my colleagues- the informants of my survey and wish them success.

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